

Deliverable D5.5 – Communication and Outreach Results

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WP5 – Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Activities

WP leader – Brainport Development

PROJECT TITLE

COORDINATING AND PILOTING ACTIONS TOWARDS ERA-HUBS AS INTER- AND INTRA-REGIONAL ECOSYSTEMS FOR KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

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Table of contents

<i>Executive Summary</i>	4
<i>List of abbreviation/Nomenclature</i>	5
<i>Table of figures</i>	6
1 Introduction	7
2 Tools and channels for the communication strategy	0
3 Dissemination strategy and activities	3
3.1 Overview of Communication and Dissemination activities organised	6
3.2 Interviews	8
3.3 Overview of communication materials developed	10
4 Conclusion	0

Executive Summary

This document, titled "Communication and Outreach results", provides a comprehensive overview of the Communication and Dissemination activities and materials which have been developed and utilised throughout the implementation period of the project. It compares the realisation and performance of the project compared to the submitted proposal and serves to quantify activities in support of evaluation of Work Package 5.

List of abbreviation/Nomenclature

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
DX.X	Deliverable Number
ERA	European Research Area
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
SA	SELF-ASSESSMENT
TX.X	Task number
R&I	Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package

Table of figures

Table 1 COOPERATE communication and dissemination tools and channels.....	2
Table 2 COOPERATE dissemination activities.....	3
Table 3 Summary of COOPERATE communication activities and related KPIs	5
Table 4 Overview of Communication and Dissemination activities organised	8
Table 5 Overview of organisations interviewed	9
Table 6 Overview of communication materials developed.....	11

1 Introduction

Throughout the implementation period of the COOPERATE project efforts have been placed on communicating and disseminating information about the project, its activities as well as results. This work was organised through Work Package 5: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities. Previous deliverables such as D5.1 Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination Release I and D5.4 Communication and Outreach Strategy outlined the communication and dissemination strategy which would be deployed. This deliverable serves to quantify the performance of the project with regards to communication and dissemination and to provide a comprehensive overview of all activities undertaken as well as the materials developed.

Please note that due to the public publication level of this deliverable, and bearing in mind Privacy/GDPR regulations, names of individuals, or any information which can be used to identify individual persons, have not been included in this document.

2 Tools and channels for the communication strategy

COOPERATE has developed and implemented the following communication tools that has allowed to raise awareness among the identified stakeholders.

Communication tools	Realisation
<p>Project branding: visual identity will be developed as a tool to create branding around the project and properly convey the message of its purpose to the main stakeholders. The COOPERATE visual identity will be incorporated in all project's materials. It will contribute to the project's visibility, noticeability and relatability.</p>	<p>The visual identity of the COOPERATE project, as presented in the submitted proposal, was applied across all communication tools/platforms (e.g. website, social media, events, etc.) and materials (e.g. newsletters, videos, flyers, etc.), thereby contributing to the projects' visibility and recognisability among stakeholders.</p>
<p>COOPERATE project website: a website dedicated to the project will be launched by M3. It will be the most relevant communication channels since it will: a) host the tools for interaction with the community of stakeholders and ecosystems; b) host all documents and materials produced as part of the COOPERATE methodology; c) display news, information, events and results; d) simplify the communication with the general public.</p>	<p>The COOPERATE website was successfully launched by M3 and since served as a central communication platform of the project. It not only informed visitors on the objectives of the COOPERATE project, but allowed for easy access to the key project outputs and materials. Furthermore, the website was used for the deployment of the Call for Champions and hosts the COOPERATE Self-Assessment Tool, Playbook, Toolbox and Platform.</p>
<p>Social media: COOPERATE will primarily use LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube as communication support channels. These channels will be used to sustain an assertive dialogue throughout and beyond the project with the target groups. COOPERATE YouTube channel will be created as a repository for the videos of the project.</p>	<p>During the implementation, LinkedIn was used as primary social media platform. This was primarily due to the nature of the content produced and the fact that the targeted audience(s) are active on this platform. YouTube and Spotify were also utilised as repositories for the videos and podcasts which were produced.</p>
<p>E-newsletters: a newsletter every 3 months is planned to inform the community of the progresses made and next events/activities in the project, including scientific and policy related news in an easy-to-read format. The newsletter will be shared through e-mail and archived in .pdf version on the website.</p>	<p>A total of 10 newsletters were produced and sent to recipients (one every 3 months). These newsletters included information related to project activities and news, more profound insights on the COOPERATE methodology and ERA Hubs framework, as well as information related to relevant policy developments. The newsletters</p>

	were also made available through the project website.
<p>Press releases: short “press release-style” will be prepared at the beginning and at the end of the project and in any other moments of the project when significant milestones are achieved, and events organised.</p>	<p>3 press releases were developed, shared and made available through the COOPERATE website. The press releases addressed the project launch, Call for Champions, and project closure.</p>
<p>Videos: 3 videos will be created to maximise project’s impact. A video will be created to present the project, the underlying methodology and the activities. During the lifetime of the project, another two videos will be created to present co-creation activities and main achievements, to tease the upcoming COOPERATE events, to present the main outcomes of events. At the end of the project, a video showcasing the results and impacts of the project.</p>	<p>A total of 10 videos were produced over the course of the implementation period. These included an introductory video to the COOPERATE project, a video of the mid-term event organised in conjunction with the ERA Fabric project, a video of the final event, also organised in conjunction with the ERA Fabric project, and an after-movie of the final event. Additionally, video recordings of the podcasts and the COOPERATE intervention at the 2024 WIRE conference (this video is not included in the overall tally) are also available. All videos are accessible through the COOPERATE YouTube channel.</p>
<p>Podcasts: based on the project public deliverables and all the outcomes of COOPERATE, we will prepare 6 podcasts highlighting the main takeaways and making them “easy-to-understand and to digest”” for non-scientific stakeholders and the general public. The podcasts will be released on the most relevant podcast channels.</p>	<p>Over the course of the project, a total of 6 podcasts were delivered and made available through Spotify and YouTube (video recordings to complement the audio). The podcasts featured various guests and were focussed on discussing aspects related to ERA and ERA Hubs, (development of) R&I ecosystems and highlighted specific real-life cases of successful innovation ecosystems.</p>
<p>Communication kit (Factsheets, Flyers and Posters): in the same logic as the podcasts, the objective is to translate sometimes difficult scientific content in an easy-to-understand manner. The project team will product 4 factsheets and communicate them through its channels. Further, based on the project’s identity, a flyer (e-format)</p>	<p>Through the implementation period the following products were delivered; a project poster, a flyer (which was updated during the implementation of the action), and three factsheets (one focussing on the Lines of Action as part of the COOPERATE methodology, one focussing on the COOPERATE Playbook, and one focussing on the Call</p>

<p>illustrating the COOPERATE objectives and activities will be created to be distributed and used during all the events. A poster will be created at mid-term to highlight the outcomes and future outcomes of the project.</p>	<p>for Champions). The availability of the produced materials was shared through our regular communication channels such as the newsletters and social media. All products can be accessed through the project website.</p>
<p>Storytelling: specifically addressing the “citizens”, COOPERATE activities and results will be shared in an adequate manner to foster trust in emerging technologies and acceptance by society.</p>	<p>Where possible, the more theoretical and abstract content of the project was translated and conveyed in an easy-to-understand manner. Despite this, addressing and reaching citizens (i.e. the general public) was very challenging. The topic addressed by the COOPERATE project is not one which naturally draws attention as it is quite far removed from the day-to-day lives of the general public. Additionally, the nature of the work of the COOPERATE project, as well as the set ambitions (stimulating/facilitating ecosystem development, providing policy recommendations, etc.) caters more to a professional (and specific) audience.</p>

Table 1 COOPERATE communication and dissemination tools and channels

3 Dissemination strategy and activities

The table below highlights the activities to be undertaken in the context of Work Package 5 that have been taken directly from the approved project proposal. For each activity, the realisation and ensuing deviation from the target value has been included.

Table 2 COOPERATE dissemination activities

Awareness of the project and Call for Champions			
Activities to achieve the objective	Targeted number of activities	Realisation	% Deviation from target
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness raising at regional and national scale • Awareness raising throughout EU • Project website, comms tools, etc. 	3 webinars / seminars	4	133%
	At least 5 presentations in Eurotech events	3	60%
	10 quarterly project newsletters	10	100%
Performance indicator(s)		Realisation	
~ 150 stakeholders: experts, social partners, businesses and policy makers attracted to the events		~ 250+	100%

Engagement of researchers and innovators			
Activities to achieve the objective	Targeted number of activities	Realisation	% Deviation from target
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct contacts through partners' networks • Access to EU databases of existing projects • Co-creation sessions • Interviews with experts 	280 direct contacts with experts and e.g. ERC & FET projects and deep-tech innovators	350+	100%
	13 co-creation sessions	15	115% (if 14 then 108%)
	24 interviews	28	117%
Performance indicator(s)		Realisation	
~ 200 actively participating		~ 250+	100%

Engagement of larger community			
Activities to achieve the objective	Targeted number of activities	Realisation	% Deviation from target
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct contacts through partners' networks • Synergies EU initiatives • Webinars for uptake of emerging tech • Scenario workshops 	200 direct contacts with stakeholders (e-mails)	400+	100%
	1 validation session during co-creation	2	200%
	6 podcasts	6	100%
Performance indicator(s)		Realisation	
50 participants per webinar		112 total (average 28)	56%
24 stakeholders interviewed		28 interviews held	117%

Involvement of public authorities			
Activities to achieve the objective	Targeted number of activities	Realisation	% Deviation from target
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bi-lateral meetings and consultations • Policy recommendations 	2 large meetings and consultations	4	200%
	1 White Paper	1	100%
Performance indicator(s)		Realisation	
At least 20 EU, national and regional policy makers attracted		29	145%

Consolidation of COOPERATE community			
Activities to achieve the objective	Targeted number of activities	Realisation	% Deviation from target
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in events 	4 fairs/events attended	7	175%
	4 Fact Sheets and 1 Poster	3	75%

3.1 Overview of Communication and Dissemination activities organised

The table below provides a complete overview of all Communication and Dissemination activities which have been organised. This includes, amongst others, co-creation sessions, webinars or seminars, workshops, podcasts, events organised and COOPERATE interventions organised in the framework of other events.

No.	Type of activity	Date	Location	(Event) Title
1	Co-creation session	18/4/2023	Online	Mission and thematic scope
2	Co-creation session	14/6/2023	Lyngby, DK	Lines of action
3	Co-creation session	25/9/2023	Online	Governance of ERA Hubs as an EU initiative
4	Co-creation session	10/11/2023	Bilbao, ES	Governance of ERA Hubs in EU regions - Organised in the framework of the 10 th WOIC Conference
5	Co-creation session	16/11/2023	Lyngby, DK	Introducing initial concepts
6	Co-creation session	8/3/2024	Online	Testing initial concepts
7	Co-creation session	5/6/2024	Prague, CZ	Validation and initial recommendations piloting playbook toolbox
8	Co-creation session	25/6/2024	Online	Testing revised concepts
9	Co-creation session	19/9/2024	Brussels, BE	Validation and initial recommendations piloting playbook toolbox
10	Co-creation session	23/9/2024	Online	With CZ, DK & NL Pilot
11	Co-creation session	7/11/2024	Berkeley, US	Recommendations, as well as ERA Hub definition and interplay playbook/toolbox and Self-Assessment for maturity levels - Organised in the framework of the 11 th WOIC Conference
12	Co-creation session	9/4/2025	Eindhoven, NL	Broader community - Co-creation session with EuroTeQ partners
13	Co-creation session	19/5/2025	Munich, DE	Broader community - Co-creation session with EuroTech partners
14	Co-creation session	27/5/2025	Online	With Call for Champions - Co-creation session with Call for Champions winners (Phase II piloting)
15	Co-creation session	5/6/2025	Brussels, BE	Broader community – Co-creation session at Final Brussels event
1	Webinar/seminar	13/6/2023	Brussels, BE	‘Which is the role of higher education institutions in the innovation system

				from a European perspective'
2	Webinar/seminar	9/10/2024	Online	Call for Champions informative webinar
3	Webinar/seminar	10/10/2024	Online	Call for Champions informative webinar
4	Webinar/seminar	15/10/2024	Online	Call for Champions informative webinar
1	Workshop	22/3/2024	Prague, CZ	Czech pilot workshop
2	Workshop	10/9/2024	Eindhoven, NL	Dutch pilot workshop
3	Workshop	17/9/2024	Lyngby	Danish pilot workshop
4	Workshop	23/4/2025	Online	Centre-Val de Loire workshop
5	Workshop	24/06/2025	Online	Lotz workshop
1	Expert Talk	29/9/2023	Den Bosch, NL	UNLimited festival
2	Expert Talk	19/11/2023	Brussels, BE	ERRIN Policy Working Group on ERA Hubs
3	Expert Talk	19/3/2024	Budapest, HU	Smart Budapest Forum
4	Expert Talk	1/5/2024	The Hague, NL	FP10 Stakeholder event
5	Expert Talk	4/6/2024	Prague, CZ	Expert talk on University 4.0
6	Expert Talk	2/10/2024	Brussels, BE	ERRIN SEFS Working Group
7	Expert Talk	13/11/2024	Budapest, HU	WIRE conference (Week of Innovative Regions in Europe)
8	Expert Talk	27/11/2024	Eindhoven, NL	DG-RTD visit to Eindhoven University of Technology
9	Expert Talk	19/2/2025	Online	Community of practice, HUBS 5.0 Working Group
1	Eurotech event	16/11/2023	Lyngby, DK	EuroTech Innovation Day
2	Eurotech event	9/4/2025	Eindhoven, NL	EuroTeQ workshop
3	Eurotech event	19/5/2025	Munich, DE	EuroTech at TUM
1	Events attended	15/6/2023	Brussels, BE	Regional Insights – Challenges and Innovative Approaches for Further Developing R&I Ecosystems in Europe in line with the ERA Policy Agenda
2	Events attended	11/10/2023	Brussels, BE	Universities as Drivers of innovation in European Regional Ecosystems
3	Events attended	10/11/2023	Bilbao, ES	WOIC 2023 – including a Policy Session
4	Events attended	28/11/2023	Barcelona, ES	Smart Specialisation (S3) Forum 2023

5	Events attended	31/1/2024	Brussels, BE & online	Research and innovation for sustainable growth: the case of Bergamo and Brescia ecosystems
6	Events attended	19/9/2024	Brussels, BE	ERA Conference
7	Events attended	10/10/2024	Lyngby, DK	Stakeholder presentation Linkoping Science Park
8	Events attended	11/12/2024	Rimini, IT	Smart Specialisation (S3) Forum 2024
9	Events attended	19/5/2025	Porto, PT	RSA Annual conference 2025
1	Large events organised	19/9/2024	Brussels, BE	COOPERATE & ERA Fabric midterm event
2	Large events organised	5/6/2025	Brussels, BE	COOPERATE & ERA Fabric final event
1	Podcast	29/10/2024	Eindhoven, NL	Episode I: Global introduction of ERA Hubs & R&I Ecosystems
2	Podcast	29/10/2024	Eindhoven, NL	Episode II: Case Brainport Eindhoven
3	Podcast	21/1/2025	Genova, IT	Episode III: Working in innovation ecosystems
4	Podcast	21/12/2025	Genova, IT	Episode IV: DTU Skylab as living lab for innovation and entrepreneurship
5	Podcast	4/6/2025	Brussels, BE	Episode V: IDEA Consult
6	Podcast	4/6/2025	Brussels, BE	Episode VI: Case Prague

Table 4 Overview of Communication and Dissemination activities organised

3.2 Interviews

A total of 28 interviews were held throughout the implementation period of the COOPERATE project. The list below identifies the various organisations which participated in the interviews (N.B. names and job title/roles have not been included due to privacy reasons).

Interviews	
1	Eindhoven University of Technology
2	IDEA Consult
3	Eindhoven University of Technology
4	Science City Lyngby
5	Eindhoven University of Technology

6	Czech Technical University in Prague
7	Czech Technical University in Prague
8	Lubanski Holding
9	Science City Lyngby
10	Orestad Innovation City Copenhagen
11	Technical University of Denmark
12	Danish Ministry of Higher Education and Science
13	Technical University of Denmark
14	Brainport Development
15	City of Helmond
16	Innovation Quarter
17	Eindhoven University of Technology
18	Municipality of Eindhoven
19	Games for Health
20	SMART Photonics
21	Province of North-Brabant
22	Philips Electronics
23	Brainport Development
24	Brainport Development
25	Municipality of Eindhoven
26	Eindhoven University of Technology
27	Eindhoven University of Technology
28	Eindhoven University of Technology

Table 5 Overview of organisations interviewed

3.3 Overview of communication materials developed

The following table presents an overview of all materials developed and utilized to communicate about the COOPERATE project and to disseminate information related to, among others, background information, activities, results and policy developments.

Material	Link
COOPERATE Poster	https://tinyurl.com/4arz25fx
COOPERATE Poster TU/e Research Day	https://tinyurl.com/2hxxf8sk
Factsheet – Seven Lines of Action	https://tinyurl.com/34s33hj5
Factsheet – COOPERATE	https://tinyurl.com/2dh6rphs
Factsheet – COOPERATE Playbook	https://tinyurl.com/4ybw4ayj
COOPERATE Flyer	https://tinyurl.com/57j23znw
Newsletter 1 – May 2023	https://tinyurl.com/5bzmrkdb
Newsletter 2 – June 2023	https://tinyurl.com/mv4uzc4t
Newsletter 3 – September 2023	https://tinyurl.com/9c8t64zz
Newsletter 4 – December 2023	https://tinyurl.com/4y3pk2yz
Newsletter 5 – March 2024	https://tinyurl.com/mrcpv76k
Newsletter 6 – June 2024	https://tinyurl.com/5fpz6va5
Newsletter 7 – September 2024	https://tinyurl.com/yc2e9cc8
Newsletter 8 – December 2024	https://tinyurl.com/wupwrsjj
Newsletter 9 – March 2025	https://tinyurl.com/yt73pftw
Newsletter 10 – June 2025	https://tinyurl.com/29h8rmnj
Press release – COOPERATE Kick-off	https://tinyurl.com/bdz6y2s4
Press release – Call for Champions	https://tinyurl.com/3nsb4ndz
Press release – The Future of ERA Hubs	https://tinyurl.com/53scaacs
Policy Brief	https://tinyurl.com/4psjuakw
Policy White Paper	https://tinyurl.com/56e3bud6

Video: COOPERATE – Lines of Action	https://tinyurl.com/pzdt52hm
Video: Midterm event ERA Fabric and COOPERATE	https://tinyurl.com/m7e6wbu4
Video: WIRE 2024 Conference – Succes stories from winning projects (COOPERATE)	https://tinyurl.com/8a23s4ep
Video: COOPERATE Event 'ERA Hubs: Enhancing Knowledge Valorisation in Regional R&I Ecosystems'	https://tinyurl.com/mjujv7nd
Video: Testimonial COOPERATE project at final event	https://tinyurl.com/3z7jkwvr
Video: Testimonial University of Lodz at COOPERATE final event	https://tinyurl.com/23mejaax
Video: Testimonial University of Orléans at COOPERATE final event	https://tinyurl.com/5ybzft2n

Table 6 Overview of communication materials developed

4 Conclusion

The communication and outreach activities of the COOPERATE project have been instrumental in fostering awareness, engagement and impact across a diverse group of stakeholders. Through the implementation of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy, Work Package 5 translated the project's complex methodology and framework into accessible content tailored to a range of audiences, from policy makers and researchers to innovation practitioners and, where possible, the general public.

Throughout the implementation period, the project has often met, and in some cases exceeded, its communication and dissemination targets. The project strived to have a strong online and offline presence through consistent uploads and postings on its LinkedIn profile and attending a broad range of relevant events. The communication and dissemination activities were supported by materials such as the project website, factsheets, flyers, etc. which contributed to a wide outreach. Additionally, efforts were placed on communicating and disseminating information related to the direct outputs of the COOPERATE project, such as the Policy Briefs, SELF-ASSESSMENT, PLAYBOOK, TOOLBOX and PLATFORM. These efforts contribute to the future exploitation and uptake of these results.

Overall, the communication and dissemination activities have supported the COOPERATE project's overall aims of developing the ERA Hub concept and methodology, thereby encouraging ecosystem development and attempting to strengthen interregional collaboration.